

Deliverable D6.5

Pilot (PT) Technical report and achieved results (1|2)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	2
Document Contributors	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	3
Table of contents	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Pilot overview	6
2 Implementation of technologies	8
2.1 Definition of requirements and characteristics of the data inputs (Task 3.1)	8
2.2 Development of sensors, automation and process control (Task 3.2)	8
2.3 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for mobile machinery (Task 3.3)	10
2.4 ICT Platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)	12
2.5 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)	12
2.6 Integration BIM (Task 4.4)	12
2.7 Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)	13
2.8 Energy efficiency and environmental effects (Task 5.3)	13
3 Results	14
3.1 Weighting scales	14
3.2 Mobile equipment sensors	14
3.3 KPI definition	14
4 Impact assessment	15
5 Future	16
6 Conclusions	17
List of Figures	18

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
RP	Reporting Period
PRC	Project Research Committee
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

AGREPOR is a Portuguese aggregates producer with 10 active quarries and owned by the major Portuguese cement producer CIMPOR.

AGREPOR has a wide variety of quarries (granite, limestone, dolomite and gypsum) and supplies a wide variety of public and private customers that operate for instance in public works, RMC, fertilizers, lime production, cement, concrete, ballast, mortar, etc.

Agrepur pilot site is Alenquer quarry that is located near Lisbon, extracted limestone, with a crushing and screening plant for aggregates production. The crushing and screening plant is subject to the implementations provided by DigiEcoQuarry.

- Models for quarry operations.
- Devices for automation of the treatment plant.
- Monitoring sensors and analysis tools for mobile machinery.
- BIM.
- Artificial Intelligence algorithms.
- H&S technologies.
- Environmental simulation platform.

Figure 1 View of CIMPOR's Alenquer quarry plant.

In CIMPOR's site, the autonomous and intelligent system for aggregates transportation from crushing to stock, storage and external transport traceability (KTA3.1&3.2) will be implemented with the focus on rationalising energy consumption and using equipment. Main areas monitored will be levels of the silos, analysis of the stock zone for prioritisation on transport, remote and autonomous interpretation of storage locations. The installation of technologies that enable an autonomous management will allow prioritising the aggregates to be transported, optimising routes, transport speed and deposition sites with all security safeguards, validating and demonstrating these DigiEcoQuarry solutions.

For external transport, the validation of the technologies that enable full traceability from the quarry to the customer will be demonstrated by ensuring route optimisation in terms of the best possible route that minimises transportation time and fuel consumption, Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and communication to customer and quarry (dispatch), sharing of inter-fleet information to adjust the travel speed and to guarantee just-in-time in congested unloading sites. Other aspects that will be validated in terms of storage to external transport connection will be the correct identification of the aggregate to be loaded, silo discharge control, correct truck positioning without spilling and cargo viability and communication to driver.

From IT point of view, Platform design has been implemented (WP4 – KTA 4.3), BIM models (WP4 – KTA 4.1) and AI algorithms (WP4 – KTA 4.2) as well as H&S & environmental system management (WP5 – KTA 5 and KTA 6).

2 Implementation of technologies

At the beginning of July 2022, the activities carried out in Alenquer pilot sites have consisted mainly in the acquisition of data coming from 11 sensors and 2 cameras installed until now in the mobile equipment. This allows to create a more structured and consisting of database representing a data history, monitoring the performance of mobile equipment (e.g. number of loads, downtime, etc..).

At the end of June 2023, the scales were installed in the conveyor belts. Once integrated into SCADA, this system will help us to monitor and optimize the crushing plant.

2.1 Definition of requirements and characteristics of the data inputs (Task 3.1)

This task entails the identification of all the sources for inputs and outputs in the quarry processes. Agrepor has been working with partners providing inputs and relevant information to proceed with the needed development.

2.2 Development of sensors, automation, and process control (Task 3.2)

Installation of weighing system has been performed on week 26-30 June. Weighing system supplied by ARCO has been installed on 8 conveyor belts, namely 3 conveyor belts upstream the crushing plant, and 5 at the discharge of aggregates silos. Data is collected by a computer and stored locally in a PC. This data will be integrated in the SCADA that is being developed also by ARCO and then uploaded to the Data Lake. This will allow real time information on the plant operation, thus improving the productivity and the energy consumption. Furthermore, it will be possible to have a detailed record of stoppages, bottle necks and malfunctions that can be used by the quarry management in order to support decisions and have a continuous improvement approach.

Figure 2 Weight system composed of (from left to right) weigh celula and encoder.

Figure 3 Weight system consisting of 5 scales on the silo's conveyor belts.

Figure 4 Control system in the silo's room.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 Control system in crushing plant control room.

2.3 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for mobile machinery (Task 3.3)

Going towards the direction of the development of monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery eleven sensors were installed, namely in the drill-rig, wheel loaders and dump trucks, and one external transport truck.

Furthermore, 2 of these sensors have a camera that record images of the working environment. These devices record continuously georeferenced data that is available in abaut's web portal where it is possible to consult relevant data of the equipment usage, such as working and idle time, speed, loading and dumping areas, etc. To add value to this equipment georeferenced data, the quarry is virtually divided in several areas, making thus possible to assign the machine data to specific activities.

Figure 7 Photo of the sensor in a wheel loader's.

Figure 8 Grafics from the analytics about's portal.

2.4 ICT Platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)

Meetings have been held with AKKODIS for supporting platform design implementation and defining the format in which the data are transmitted to the Data Lake.

Data entry is done manually on the platform.

The intention is for the automaton to constantly communicate with the Data Lake, sending strings that contain most of the data accessible from the Scada system. ARCO has not yet put the SCADA system into operation.

Actions	ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process	Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for AGREPOR-CIMPOR	11/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	ABAUT	String	16/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	ABAUT	String	17/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	about		17/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	ABAUT	String	17/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for AGREPOR-CIMPOR	31/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for AGREPOR-CIMPOR	31/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	Extraction (KTA1)-Drilling	Loading and Hauling	About data for Transport, Regions Projects and Machines 31/01/2023		15/02/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Orthophoto DEQ 2021	Orthophoto of the quarry created for the DEQ project in 2021	Orthophoto of the quarry created for the DEQ project in 2021	02/02/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>	13	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	transport	Transport about: PS CIMPOR		15/02/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	14	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	transport	Transport about: PS CIMPOR		15/02/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	15	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	transport	Transport about: PS CIMPOR		15/02/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	16	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	transport	Transport about: PS CIMPOR		15/02/2023

Figure 9 List of files uploaded to Data Lake.

2.5 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)

CIMPOR supported SIGMA and UPM in obtaining data to analyse our water consumption, even though we don't have this data automated or parameterised in specific consumption zones.

Sigma installed two dust sensors in our facilities analysing the best places to do it.

2.6 Integration BIM (Task 4.4)

Photos of Alenquer pilot site and AutoCAD drawings of the plant were provided to APP for the creation of BIM model. Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a process for creating and managing information on engineering and construction projects across the project lifecycle. This tool allows to virtually navigate through the plant, interacting with the different assets (e.g. screens, crushers, conveyor belts). Each single assets contains static data like manuals, spare parts list and technical specifications but also dynamic data, for example electrical consumption, production rate and other information acquired by installed sensors, thanks to the data exchange with Data Lake.

Figure 10 BIM roadmap.

2.7 Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)

One of main concerns in the quarry activity is the interaction between man and machine. The run over risk is present in the daily operation and so the development of systems supported by AI to predict and warn in time such events are being developed. This system is built upon a camera system that can provide real time data to be analysed. The preferred locations of the cameras were provided to ITK and the system is being developed to on a second stage install in the field.

2.8 Energy efficiency and environmental effects (Task 5.3)

Relevant data and information were provided to MUL and CHAL in order to develop a reliable simulation platform for assessing environmental influence of the quarrying processes. (Plantsmith).

3 Results

3.1 Weighting scales

To properly manage a quarry, it is crucial to have accurate and updated data easily accessible. When there is no automatic systems to measure validate compile and transmit information, the majority of the information is estimated based on models or information not always suitable. The installation of equipment that can collect reliable and easily accessible data is thus crucial to properly conduct the operation. This quick and precise action has a major impact in the productivity the right use of resources and energy consumption. The installation of weighing scales in the conveyor belts, namely 8, are providing the data required to manage the plant. The precision of such data has been proven so far to be adequate but further tests need to be done in order to have a full confidence.

3.2 Mobile equipment sensors

Considering the work environment, namely the fact that it is an open space with approximately 70ha of working area, in weather conditions where sometimes the visibility is reduced, the existence of a tool were it is possible in almost real time to have a general comprehension of the location of the machines as such major indicators on their operation is an aid that can increase significantly the optimization of the equipment, with major return on profitability, energy savings and safety.

3.3 KPI definition

Reaching a precise definition of the KPIs is important, so that it is possible and reliable to obtain the data for KPIs calculation and the KPI effectively allows to monitor the performance studied.

4 Impact assessment

The process of implementing DEQ system, equipment's and technology is still on going, thus it is difficult at this stage to assess the today impact. Nevertheless, the expectations that exist for AGREPOR Alenquer quarry are high considering that in what concerns these issues we are starting almost from the beginning.

More detailed data, moreover production, environment and health and safety, will certainly improve the assessment and achieve the project goals.

5 Future

As regards as WP6.5 is concerned, thanks to the data collected through the weighing scales in the conveyor belts, the sensors installed in the mobile equipment so far, we expect gradual improvements thanks to the development and implementation of the technologies and solutions researched by the other project partners. Also, an improvement in energy consumption, efficiency, productivity and water consumption is expected.

The path that has to be done till the end of the project, as such the innovative approaches and results obtained, surely will be used as reference and extrapolated to all the quarry industry companies contributing to a better use of finite resources, in a more efficient, rational and sustainable way.

6 Conclusions

Activities at our site in Alenquer so far have mainly consisted of providing data, supporting and implementing technologies, solutions and research in collaboration with the other project partners.

As a pilot site, it has been essential to share our knowledge of the processes, thus communicating the needs from a production and operational point of view and identifying where there is room for improvement and the directions to take in order to improve the KPIs. The first fundamental step in improving production performance (improving the KPIs) is to acquire sufficient data to better monitor the processes, thus also having enough information to calculate the KPIs and estimate the evolution of performance. Scales, sensors and cameras have been installed, and in future the data will be sent automatically to the IQS so that it will be possible to study process performance in detail.

List of Figures

Figure 1 View of CIMPOR's Alenquer quarry plant.....	6
Figure 2 Weight system composed of (from left to right) weigh celula and encoder.....	8
Figure 3 Weight system consisting of 5 scales on the silo's conveyors belts.....	9
Figure 4 Control system in the silo's room.....	9
Figure 5 and Figure 6 Control system in crushing plant control room.....	10
Figure 7 Photo of the sensor in a wheel loader's.....	11
Figure 8 Grafics from the analytics about's portal.....	11
Figure 9 List of files uploaded to Data Lake.....	12
Figure 10 BIM roadmap.....	12